

0.1 mol), a solution of sodium hydroxide (8.96 g, 0.244 mo) was added slowly with stirring. The contents were heated until most of the liquid evaporated and the residue was treated with water (250 ml) and cooled. The clear solution was then acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid and the resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol-water (3:1) solvent, (13.91 g, 16%), m.p. 243° (Found: C, 52.49; H, 3.80; S, 8.69. $C_{16}H_{14}O_3S$ requires: C, 52.4; H, 3.85; S, 8.75%); ν_{max} (KBr) 920-880 br (OH, o-o-p def.), 1241 (C-O-C asym.), 1140, 1290 (S=O asym. and sym., respectively), 1740 (C=O) and 3430 cm^{-1} (OHstr).

p,p'-Bis(*N*-arylthioureidocarbonylmethoxyphenyl) sulphone (1): A mixture of *p,p'*-bis(carboxymethoxy)diphenylsulphone (3.66 g, 0.01 mol), thionyl chloride (2.5 ml) and chloroform (10 ml) was refluxed for 6 h. Excess thionyl chloride was then removed under reduced pressure and the residue was refluxed with phenyl thiourea (3.04 g, 0.02 mol) in chloroform (10 ml) for 3 h. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol-dioxane (3:1) solvent, (4.63 g, 73%), m.p. 146° (Found: C, 56.71; H, 4.09; N, 8.84. $C_{30}H_{26}N_4O_6S_2$ requires: C, 56.76; H, 4.12; N, 8.82%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1250 (C-O-C asym.), 1145, 1295 (S=O asym. and sym., respectively), 1670 (C=O amide-I sec.), 1510 (NH def. +CN str., amide-II sec.), 1295 (NH def. +CN str., amide-III sec.); δ (DMSO- d_6) 4.80 (4H, s, $2 \times ArOCH_2$), 7.02-8.00 (18H, m, $4 \times ArH$) and 10.04 (4H, s, $2 \times NHCSNHCO$).

Similarly, other phenyl thioureas were condensed with acid chloride (Table 1).

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Prof. A. R. Parikh, Head, Department of Chemistry, Saurashtra University, Rajkot, for facilities and to the Gujarat State Government for awarding Research Scholarship to one of them (R.N.V.) and to U.G.C., New Delhi for awarding Junior Research Fellowship to the other (K.P.R.). The authors are also thankful to the Director, I. I. T., Bombay for the spectral data.

References

1. D. V. GORDON, L. E. EUGENE and R. C. BROWN, Ger. Pat. 3 247 581/1982; J. L. ARCHIBALD and TERENCE, US Pat. 4 563 466/1986; J. S. SHUKLA and I. AHMED, *J. Indian Ch. m. Soc.*, 1980, 57, 950; O. HAZYO *Jap. Kakai Tokkyo Koho*, 1980, 80, 72, 159; D. R. HAUGWITZ and V. B. MAURER, US Pat. 4 21 8396/1980.
2. H. WITZFL, T. WAGNER-JAUREGG and H. VANDERBANK, *Chem. Ber.*, 1948, 81, 417.
3. F. KAVANAGH, "Analytical Microbiology", Academic, New York, 1963, p. 126.

Synthesis of some 2(*H*),4(*H*)-1,2,4-Triazino[3,4-*c*]-1,4-benzoxazin-5-ones

M. B. HOGALE* and B. P. NIKAM

Department of Chemistry, Shivaji University, Kolhapur-416 004

Manuscript received 29 February 1988, revised 31 May 1988, accepted 18 July 1988

It has been reported that some fused triazoles of 1,4-benzoxazin-3(2*H*)-ones exhibit diuretic¹ and other pharmacological properties^{2,3}. In view of these findings, the present paper describes the synthesis and characterisation of 2(*H*),4(*H*)-1,2,4-triazino[3,4-*c*]-1,4-benzoxazin-5-ones from the corresponding 1,4-benzoxazin-3(2*H*)-ones (Scheme 1), and study their antibacterial activity.

Scheme 1

As a representative case *o*-halophenol on condensation with chloroacetamide in ethanol in

Chart 1

presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate gave rise to a compound 1a⁴. This on being refluxed with ethyl bromoacetate in presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate gave 4-carboethoxymethyl-1,4-benzoxazin-3(2H)-one (2a). The mass spectral fragmentation of 4-carboethoxymethyl-1,4-benzoxazin-3(2H)-one is as shown in Chart 1. Compound 2a on being refluxed with hydrazine hydrate (80%) in ethanol yielded 4-hydrazinomethyl-1,4-benzoxazin-3(2H)-one (3a). The mass fragmentation pattern is shown in Chart 1. 2(H),4(H) 8,10-Dibromo-1,2,4-triazino[3,4-c]-1,4-benzoxazin-5-one (4a) was syn-

thesised by heating 3b with ammonium acetate in glacial acetic acid. The analytical and physical data of the compounds are reported in Table 1.

Antibacterial activity: The hydrazinomethyl (3a-f) and triazino (4a-d) derivatives were tested for their antibacterial activity by cup-plate method⁵. The activity was tested (1 mg ml⁻¹) in acetone against gram-positive *Strepto. pneumonia* and *Staphylo. aureus* and gram-negative *E. coli* and *S. typhosa*. The compounds having bromo and chloro substituents in benzene ring were found to be

TABLE 1 - ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 2-4

Compd. no.	Y ₁ [¶]	Y ₂ [¶]	Y ₃	M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	Analysis% : Found / (Calcd.)		
							C	H	N
2a	H	H	H	90	77.4	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₄ N	61.20 (61.28)	5.50 (5.53)	5.90 (5.96)
2b	Br	H	Br	245	74.1	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₄ NBr ₂	36.60 (37.02)	2.75 (2.83)	3.50 (3.60)
2c	Br	H	Cl	76	81.2	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₄ NBrCl	41.30 (41.56)	3.10 (3.18)	4.00 (4.04)
2d	Cl	H	Br	102	78.6	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₄ NBrCl	41.30 (41.56)	3.10 (3.18)	4.00 (4.04)
2e	CH ₃	H	CH ₃	96	80.4	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ O ₄ N	63.80 (63.88)	6.40 (6.46)	5.30 (5.32)
2f	Br	H	CH ₃	118	70.8	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ O ₄ NBr	47.50 (47.85)	4.20 (4.30)	4.20 (4.29)
2g	Cl	CH ₃	Br	172	82.3	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₄ NBrCl	43.00 (43.27)	3.50 (3.61)	3.80 (3.88)
2h	Cl	H	H	240	72.0	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₄ NCl	53.40 (53.43)	4.40 (4.45)	5.15 (5.19)
3a	H	H	H	165	78.6	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ O ₃ N ₂	54.25 (54.30)	4.95 (4.98)	19.00 (19.01)
3b	Br	H	Br	113	70.2	C ₁₀ H ₉ O ₃ N ₂ Br ₂	30.10 (32.00)	2.00 (2.40)	11.00 (11.20)
3c	Br	H	Cl	138	76.0	C ₁₀ H ₉ O ₃ N ₂ BrCl	35.80 (36.09)	2.65 (2.71)	12.50 (12.63)
3d	Cl	H	Br	126	68.8	C ₁₀ H ₉ O ₃ N ₂ BrCl	35.80 (36.09)	2.65 (2.71)	12.50 (12.63)
3e	Br	H	CH ₃	115	75.2	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ O ₃ N ₂ Br	42.00 (42.31)	3.80 (3.85)	13.30 (13.46)
3f	Cl	H	H	190	80.1	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ O ₃ N ₂ Cl	46.90 (46.97)	3.90 (3.91)	16.40 (16.44)
4a	Br	H	Br	146	60.0	C ₁₀ H ₇ O ₂ N ₂ Br ₂	33.20 (33.61)	1.90 (1.96)	11.60 (11.76)
4b	Br	H	Cl	186	65.2	C ₁₀ H ₇ O ₂ N ₂ BrCl	37.90 (38.16)	2.20 (2.23)	13.20 (13.36)
4c	Cl	H	Br	106	70.1	C ₁₀ H ₇ O ₂ N ₂ BrCl	37.90 (38.16)	2.20 (2.23)	13.20 (13.36)
4d	Br	H	CH	144	63.7	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₂ Br	44.55 (44.90)	3.30 (3.40)	14.10 (14.29)

more active. In comparison to the triazino derivatives, the corresponding hydrazinomethyl derivatives were found to be more active.

Experimental

M.ps. were determined in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. The structures were supported by elemental analysis tlc, uv (EtOH), ir (KBr), nmr (TFA) and mass spectral data.

General procedure. 1,4-Benzoxazin-3(2H)-one (1a) : A mixture of *o*-halophenol (0.1 mol), chloroacetamide (0.1 mol) and anhydrous K_2CO_3 (4.2 g) in ethanol (50 ml) was refluxed for 3 h in an oil-bath. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol, (70%), m.p. 170°.

4-Carboethoxymethyl-1,4-benzoxazin-3(2H)-one(2a) : A mixture of 1a (0.05 mol), bromoethylacetate (0.05 mol) and anhydrous K_2CO_3 (3.0 g) in methanol (25 ml) was refluxed for 4 h. The solvent was then removed under reduced pressure and the separated solid crystallised from ethanol to yield 2a (74.4%), m.p. 90; $C_{12}H_{13}O_4N$; λ_{max} (EtOH) 282 nm; ν_{max} 1750 (C=O ester) and 1700 cm^{-1} (C=O δ -lactum); δ 1.4 (3H, t, CH_3 ester), 4.50 (2H, NCH₂CO), 4.3 (2H, q, CH_2 ester) and 6.7–7.1 (3H, m, ArH).

4-Hydrazinomethyl-1,4-benzoxazin-3(2H)-one (3a) : A mixture of 2a (0.018 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (80%; 0.026 mol) in ethanol (10 ml) was refluxed for 15 min. On cooling, white needle shaped crystals was separated to yield 3a (80%), m.p. 165°, $C_{10}H_{11}O_3N_2$; λ_{max} (EtOH) 292 nm; ν_{max} 3300 cm^{-1} (NHNH₂); δ 2.5 (2H, br s, NH₂) and 8.2 (1H, br s, CONH exchangeable with D₂O).

2(H),4(H)-8,10-Dibromo-1,2,4-triazino [3,4-c]-1,4-benzoxazin-5-ones (4a) : A mixture of 3b (0.001 mol), ammonium acetate (0.01 mol) in glacial acetic acid (5 ml) was refluxed for 5 h. The resulting dark brown solution was cooled, poured into crushed ice and neutralised with ammonia. The solid that separated was filtered and crystallised from ethanol to yield 4a (65%), m.p. 146°; $C_{10}H_7O_3N_3Br_2$; ν_{max} 3400–3200 (NH) and 1650 cm^{-1} (C=N); δ 4.15 (2H, s, NCH₂CO), 5.2 (2H, s, OCH₂), 7.8 (1H, br s, CONH exchangeable with D₂O).

References

1. D. R. SHRIDHAR, M. JOGIBHUKTA, V. S. H. KRISHNAN, P. P. JOSHI, M. U. R. NAIDU, G. S. THAPPAR, A. KRISHNAMURTHY and G. P. THOMAS, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1984, 23, 1279.
2. D. R. SHRIDHAR, M. JOGIBHUKTA, P. P. JOSHI and P. GOPAL REDDY, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1981, 20, 132.
3. D. R. SHRIDHAR, M. JOGIBHUKTA, L. C. VISHWAKARMA, C. SESHAGIRI RAO and A. Y. JUNARKAR, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1984, 23, 445.
4. F. V. AUWERS, *Chem. Ber.*, 1926, 59, 539.
5. B. ARRET, D. P. JOHNSON and A. KRISHABAUM, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1971, 60, 1689.

Phenolic Constituents from Leaves of *Rhus semialata* Murr.

NAZNEEN PARVEEN and NIZAM UD-DIN KHAN*

Department of Chemistry, Aligarh Muslim University,
Aligarh-202 002

Manuscript received 9 March 1988, accepted 27 July 1988

THE genus *Rhus* (Anacardiaceae) consists of several species of trees shrubs and climbers. A number of chemotaxonomically significant biflavones have been isolated from *R. succedanea*¹, *R. toxicodendron*², *R. punjabensis*³ and *R. mysurensis*⁴. Bagchi *et al.*⁵ isolated only agathisflavone from the leaves of *R. semialata*. The present paper deals with the isolation and characterisation of ethyl gallate, agathisflavone, robustaflavone, amentoflavone and myricetin from the leaves of *R. semialata*. The occurrence of myricetin is the characteristic feature of the genus *Rhus*.

Leaves of *R. semialata* were collected from Royal Botanical Garden, Godawari, Lalitpur, Nepal. The dried and crushed leaves (0.5 kg) were extracted first with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) and then with acetone. The acetone extract was concentrated under reduced pressure. It gave positive colour test with Mg/HCl (orange). The crude mixture (3 g) was chromatographed on a column of silica gel (8 g); eluted with benzene, ethyl acetate, ethyl acetate–acetone (8 : 2) and then with ethyl acetate–methanol (9 : 1). RS-I was isolated from the ethyl acetate eluate. The fraction eluted with ethyl acetate–acetone (8 : 2) was found to be a mixture of biflavones (RS-II and RS-III), which were further separated by preparative tlc (benzene–pyridine–formic acid, 36 : 9 : 5). The ethyl acetate–methanol (9 : 1) eluate gave RS-IV.

RS-I was crystallised from EtOAc–acetone as yellowish solid, m.p. 155°; appeared brown in uv light and gave blue colour with alcoholic $FeCl_3$, R_f 0.50 (BPF), $C_9H_{10}O_5$ (M^+m/e 198); m/e 198 (85, M^+), 183 (15), 170 (20), 153 (100, $C_7H_8O_4$), 125 (50), 113 (10), 108 (5), 107 (15), 79 (60), 53 (25), 39 (55) and 27 (45), δ (DMSO- d_6) 1.32 (3H, t, J 7 Hz, CH_3), 4.24 (2H, q, J 7 Hz, CH_2) and 7.11 (2H, s, H-2,6). From these data and by direct comparison with an authentic sample it was found to be ethyl gallate.

The ethyl acetate–acetone fraction was further separated by preparative tlc (benzene–pyridine–formic acid, 36 : 9 : 5) as RS-II ($R_f=0.15$) and RS-III ($R_f=0.18$).

RS-II was comparable with agathisflavone⁶ but after methylation it was found to be a mixture of agathisflavone hexamethyl ether⁷ and robustaflavone hexamethyl ether⁷ on comparison with authentic samples (m.p., R_f , fluorescence in uv light).